

Recoil frame photoemission in multiphoton ionization of small polyatomic molecules: photodynamics of NO₂ probed by 400 nm femtosecond pulses.

S. Marggi Poullain^{1,5,6}, C. Elkharrat^{1,7}, W. B. Li^{1,8}, K. Veyrinas¹, J.C. Houver¹, C. Cornaggia², T. N. Rescigno³, R. R. Lucchese⁴ and D. Dowek^{1,5}

¹ Institut des Sciences Moléculaires d'Orsay, Université Paris-Sud et CNRS, Bat. 210-350, Université Paris-Sud, F-91405 Orsay Cedex, France

² Laboratoire Interactions, Dynamique et Lasers, CEA IRAMIS Saclay, Bat. 522, F-91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

³ Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Chemical Sciences, Berkeley, California 94720, USA

⁴ Department of Chemistry, Texas A&M University, College Station, 77840, USA

E-mail: danielle.dowek@u-psud.fr; smarggi@ucm.es

Abstract

We report a general method for the complete analysis of the recoil frame photoelectron angular distribution (RFPAD) in n -photon dissociative ionization of small polyatomic molecules, resulting from $(n-1)$ bound-to-bound transitions plus one-photon ionization of a neutral excited state of the target. This method relies on the decomposition of the RFPAD in terms of the $R_K(\chi, \theta_e)$ Recoil Frame Azimuthal Harmonics (RFAHs) which are the components of its Fourier expansion in ϕ_e , where χ and θ_e are the polar angles referring the polarization axis \mathbf{P} and the photoelectron momentum \mathbf{k} relative to the ion fragment recoil direction, respectively, and ϕ_e is the azimuth of \mathbf{k} relative to \mathbf{P} . The RFAH expansion method is illustrated by a detailed experimental and theoretical study of one-color multiphoton dissociative and non-dissociative ionization of the NO₂ molecule of C_{2v} symmetry induced by 400 nm femtosecond (fs) laser pulses, which involve electronic and nuclear dynamics within the pulse duration of the order of 70 fs. The reaction mechanism proposed to account for five-photon dissociative ionization of NO₂ involves the role of [R*(6a₁)⁻¹] Rydberg states populated by three-photon absorption, subsequently ionized by a fourth photon into the NO₂⁺ (X¹Σ_g⁺, ν₁, ν₂, ν₃) manifold involving autoionization of [R*(4b₂)⁻¹] Rydberg states, and linear versus bent geometry selective dissociation of NO₂⁺ (X¹Σ_g⁺, ν₁, ν₂, ν₃) by a fifth photon. The reported calculations provide a coherent picture of the experimental findings although all features are not yet well reproduced.

⁵ Authors to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

⁶ Current address : Departamento de Química Física, Facultad de Ciencias Químicas (Unidad asociada CSIC), Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain

⁷ Current address : caroline.elkharrat@gmail.com

⁸ Current address : IPOE, School of Physics Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, China

1. Introduction

In recent years, the study of molecular frame photoelectron angular distributions (MFPADs) has proven to be a most powerful means to determine the complex dipole matrix elements governing the dynamics of photoionization of molecules, their magnitude and relative phases [1,2]. From the experimental perspective, several strategies are developed to reach this goal which consist of aligning the molecular target in the laboratory frame and recording the photoelectron angular distributions (PADs) in the laboratory frame [3–5], performing rotationally resolved photoionization experiments [6], or taking advantage of dissociative ionization in electron-ion coincidence 3D momentum spectroscopy experiments to achieve molecular frame (MF) angular observables [7–9]. Besides the issue of photoionization dynamics, photoionization is most often used as a probe of the relaxation dynamics of highly excited molecular states, with the same focus to achieve molecular frame photoemission as a complete observable [10,11]. Combining molecular frame photoemission with time resolved studies in the femtosecond or subfemtosecond range, which is the appropriate time scale for characterizing the electronic dynamics and subsequent nuclear dynamics induced in the molecule by photoinduced electronic excitation or ejection of one or multiple electrons in the continuum, is now possible thanks to the advent of light sources delivering femtosecond and/or attosecond pulses in the XUV range such as HHG [12] and FELs [13], and motivates a number of ongoing developments [14].

For one photon single ionization processes induced by valence shell or inner shell excitation, a complete formalism describing the general analytical form of the $I(\chi, \theta_e, \phi_e)$ MFPAD, where χ is the molecular axis orientation with respect to the light quantization axis and (θ_e, ϕ_e) are the polar and azimuthal emission angles in the MF, has been proposed for linear molecules [15,16] and extended to the description of recoil frame photoelectron angular distributions (RFPADs) [17] for non-linear molecules. The expansion of $I(\chi, \theta_e, \phi_e)$, involving five one-dimensional $F_{LN}(\theta_e)$ functions which contain the complete dynamical information about the photoionization process, has proven to be an efficient means to extract MFPADs or RFPADs for any well defined molecular or recoil axis orientation χ . This unified formalism is well adapted for the analysis of electron-ion coincidence momentum spectroscopy experiments, in particular when using light sources with kHz repetition rates, since all recorded events for a given process contribute to the statistical quality of the MFPAD for each selected orientation of the molecule.

In this paper we address the question of the relevance of a parallel description of MF or RF photoemission when several photons are involved in the ionization process. We derive a general analytical expression for the multiphoton RFPAD which is expanded in recoil frame azimuthal harmonics (RFAH). We propose a principal component analysis (PCA) of this observable which allows for a convenient comparison between experiment and theoretical models. This method applies to multiphoton ionization (MPI) of molecules at intermediate laser intensities due to non-linear light-matter interaction in the perturbative regime, as well as to pump-and-probe time resolved studies where photoinduced dissociation is probed via ionization of the relaxing molecule, including XUV-pump XUV-probe experimental schemes.

As a prototype reaction for this study we selected one-color multiphoton ionization of the NO_2 molecule, which has C_{2v} symmetry, induced by a laser source delivering femtosecond pulses with wavelengths of about 400 nm. Photodynamics of NO_2 is a prototypical model of electron and nuclear coupled dynamics involving vibronic coupling [18] and/or conical intersections [19,20], for which a number of time-resolved studies have been performed as described in the extensive review of Wilkinson and Whitaker [21]. Although absorption of one or two 400 nm photons is likely to involve resonant excitation of intermediate valence excited states of NO_2 , in the excitation energy range corresponding to three and four photon absorption lying around 9.2 eV and 12.4 eV, respectively, the valence electronic configuration is strongly mixed with that of Rydberg states converging to the $\text{NO}_2^+(X^1\Sigma_g^+)$ ground state or $\text{NO}_2^+(a^3B_2)$ first excited state.

The pioneering time-resolved PADs in the recoil frame relying on coincident electron-ion momentum spectroscopy, probing photodissociation of NO_2 induced by absorption of three photons and ionized by absorption of a fourth photon, used 375 nm pulses of 100 fs duration with time delays varying from 350 fs up to few ps [22,23]. They were reported for an orientation of the linear polarization axis parallel to the recoil velocity, demonstrating a strongly forward-backward (FW-BW) asymmetry favoring electron emission in the direction of the NO^+ recoil with two lobes at 30° , for zero

pump-probe time delay. Reflecting the time-dependent separation of the fragments, the FW-BW asymmetry was shown to decrease for larger time delays corresponding to increasing molecular bond lengths. For zero pump-probe time delay, the dissociation and ionization both occur within the duration of a single laser pulse (100 fs) and the asymmetry was assigned to the effect of the nearby O atom on the ionization of the incipient $\text{NO}(\text{C}^2\Pi)$ state in a dissociating NO_2 Rydberg state, however no calculations have been performed to our knowledge which support this qualitative interpretation. RFPADs displaying significant FW-BW asymmetry for zero time delays were also reported using 400 nm-266 nm two color femtosecond time-resolved coincidence imaging [24]. Despite the interesting results achieved in the characterization of the reaction pathways leading to ionization and dissociation in such studies, a number of questions remain open concerning in particular the short time electronic and nuclear dynamics.

One goal of this work is therefore to provide a coherent interpretation of the multiphoton excitation scheme of NO_2 at zero pump-probe time delay and in particular to interpret the photoelectron emission in the recoil frame through the proposed detailed comparison between experimental and theoretical results. The analytical description of the multiphoton RFPAD for polyatomic molecules [2] is here adapted to the C_{2v} (or C_s) symmetry of the NO_2 molecule. Concerning photoexcitation and photoionization of NO_2 , we refer to two previous papers presenting the concepts and formalism for (i) RFPADs for one photon induced dissociative ionization of NO_2 , applied to PI into the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{b}^3\text{A}_2)$ ionic state [17] (ii) $\text{NO}^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma^+)$ - $\text{O}^-(^2\text{P})$ ion pair formation in multiphoton ionization of NO_2 induced by 400 nm femtosecond laser pulses [25] as well as to a recent report of the role of Rydberg states in photoionization of NO_2 and NO^+ , O^- ion pair formation in the 11-13 eV photon energy range [26].

New experimental results are reported for one color multi-photon ionization (MPI) of the NO_2 molecule leading to the production of NO_2^+ and NO^+ molecular ions induced by the absorption of four or five photons linearly (**P**) polarized light delivered by a femtosecond laser source set in the 400 nm wavelength range [27]. They were obtained using the vector correlation (VC) method previously developed to study one photon PI of molecules induced by VUV [9,28] or soft X ray [29] synchrotron radiation light. These results are compared with detailed calculations of the MFPADs and RFPADs for ionization of NO_2 from a selection of possible excited states and different geometries.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2 we give a brief description of the experimental set-up used for the MPI experiments performed at the Saclay Laser-matter Interaction Center (SLIC) facility as well as for a complementary investigation of one photon induced ionization in the 15.5 eV photon excitation energy range, corresponding to the energy of five 400 nm photons, performed at the DESIRS beamline at SOLEIL. In section 3 we present the main steps of the formalism leading to the expression of the multiphoton RFPADs and discuss possible strategies to compare most completely theory and experiments. The theoretical method used in the computation of the dipole matrix elements describing photoionization of super excited Rydberg states of the NO_2 molecule is described in section 4. In section 5 we report the electron-ion kinetic energy correlation diagrams (KECDs) measured for MPDI of the NO_2 molecule and the photoelectron energy spectrum for non-dissociative MPI, at 397 nm wavelength, which are compared with those obtained for single photon dissociative ionization (SPDI) and non-dissociative ionization (SPI) at $h\nu \approx 15.69$ eV, as well as the first angular observables in terms of electron and ion fragment one-dimensional (1-D) laboratory frame angular distributions reflecting the $(\mathbf{V}_e, \mathbf{P})$, and $(\mathbf{V}_{\text{NO}^+}, \mathbf{P})$ correlations. In section 6, the recoil frame photoelectron angular distributions (RFPADs) for the dominant process measured for MPDI of the NO_2 molecule are reported and their interpretation is discussed in comparison with recent calculations (sect. 7). In section 8 we propose reaction pathways and discuss its compatibility with all the measures observables. Possible implications of the present work are presented in the conclusion.

2. Experimental method

The VC electron-ion velocity spectrometer has been described in detail previously [9,28]. It is equipped with two time and position sensitive delay-line detectors (PSDs) [30] and combines time-of-flight-resolved ion-electron coincidence detection with three dimensional imaging. The interaction region is located at the center of the spectrometer and defined as the intersection of the supersonic molecular jet of NO_2 (5% seeded in He) and the light beam. Ions and electrons were extracted from the

interaction region by a dc uniform electric field and guided to their respective position sensitive detectors through an intermediate region where two focusing electrostatic lens sets (Λ_{A^+} and Λ_e) are applied. The electric extraction field was fixed between 20 and 60 V/cm for most of the results presented such that a complete 4π collection of both ions and electrons of the DPI processes of interest was ensured. For each (A^+ , e_{ph}) coincident event, the three components of the V_{A^+} ion and V_e photoelectron ejection velocity vectors are derived from the time of flight (TOF) and impact position (x , y) of the particles on their respective PSD.

The multiphoton experiments were performed at the Saclay Laser-matter Interaction Centre (SLIC) for multiphoton ionization (MPI), where two femtosecond laser facilities have been used, SOFOCKLE and PLFA, based on a Titanium-Sapphire (TiS) laser medium run at 1kHz repetition rate with 30 fs typical pulse duration as described in [25]. After frequency doubling these laser sources deliver 70-80 femtosecond (fs) pulses around 400 nm, and the laser peak intensity was kept in the 10^{10} - 10^{11} Watt/cm² range. A limited tunability for wavelengths near 400 nm (395-405 nm) was achieved on PLFA. The results presented here were performed using linearly polarized light, measurements using circularly polarized light were also carried out and will be reported in a future publication. The complementary investigation on single photon ionization (SPI) was achieved on the VUV DESIRS beamline at SOLEIL using circularly polarized light. The VC spectrometer was installed either in the SAPHIRS set-up [31] producing a molecular supersonic expansion, or mounted onto the CIEL2 ultra-high-vacuum (UHV) chamber, equipped with a double skimmer supersonic expansion, working at a standing pressure of 10^{-9} mbar [25,32]. In both cases the nozzle could be heated at 120°C which enabled us to control the suppression of the N₂O₄ dimer component formed in the molecular expansion.

When electron-ion coincidence experiments are performed combined with lasers sources at kHz repetition rate, it is necessary to control the signal rate and to keep \bar{n} the mean number of electron-ion coincidence events small, $\bar{n} \ll 1$, in order to avoid false coincidences between an ion and an electron from different events. The experiments were performed at a maximum acquisition rate of 50 coincidences per second (0.05 events/pulse) in order to ensure a true coincidence acquisition mode.

3. Multiphoton induced RFPADs: formalism

3.1. General expression of the RFPAD for multiphoton ionization of a non-linear molecule

In order to derive the general expression of the RFPAD for photoionization of a non-linear molecule induced by multiphoton absorption, we consider successive steps. Starting from the general form of the MFPAD for a one photon ionization process which is written as [2]:

$$T_{fi}^{(LP)} = \sum_{\nu} \sum_{L=0,2} \sum_{N=0}^L F_{N,\nu}^{(L)}(\theta_k) P_L^N(\cos \chi_{LP}) \cos[N(\phi_k - \gamma_{LP}) + \nu\phi_k] \quad (1)$$

for linearly polarized light, where (θ_k, ϕ_k) and (χ_{LP}, γ_{LP}) represent the polar and azimuthal angles defining the photoelectron emission direction and the light polarization axis orientation in the molecular frame (MF), respectively, and $P_L^N(\cos \chi_{LP})$ are the associated Legendre polynomials. The dipole matrix elements take part in the $F_{N,\nu}^{(L)}(\theta_k)$ one dimensional real functions [2,15] partial-wave expanded in $P_L^{|\nu|}(\cos \theta_k)$ Legendre polynomials. L derives from the expansion of the square of the electric light field and is equal to 0 or 2 for linearly polarized light, with $0 \leq N \leq L$. Finally the index ν depends on the maximum orbital angular momentum in the partial wave expansion: $-2l_{max} \leq (N + \nu) \leq 2l_{max}$, where l_{max} is characteristic of the size of the molecule and the kinetic energy of the photoelectron. The general expressions for circularly polarized light are reported in ref. [2].

Figure 1 : Schematic of the molecular frame (MF) for the NO_2 molecule where z_{MF} is the C_{2v} symmetry axis and of the recoil molecular frame (RMF) where the z_{RMF} axis is along the fragment ion recoil axis. The rotation from MF to RMF is described by the (α_R, β_R) Euler angles as shown. The molecular plane (gray) is featured by the parallelogram.

For a molecule of C_{2v} geometry such as NO_2 , the existence of the $\sigma_h (xz)$ and $\sigma_v (yz)$ reflection planes requires that only $F_{N,\nu}^{(L)}(\theta_k)$ functions with even values of ν are non-zero.

$$T_{fi}^{(LP)}(\theta_k, \phi_k, \chi_{LP}, \gamma_{LP}) = \sum_{\nu=\dots-4,-2,0,2,4,\dots} \sum_{L=0,2}^L \sum_{N=0}^L F_{N,\nu}^{(L)}(\theta_k) P_L^N(\cos \chi_{LP}) \times \cos[N(\phi_k - \gamma_{LP}) + \nu\phi_k] \quad (2)$$

If we consider e.g., a maximal orbital angular momentum of the partial wave expansion of $l_{max} = 6$, 39 $F_{N,\nu}^{(L)}(\theta_k)$ functions are involved in the expression of the MFPAD.

In a second step, we introduce another frame intrinsic to the molecule, called recoil-molecular frame (RMF), where the z_{RMF} axis is parallel to the ion recoil direction. It is derived from the MF by two rotations described by the (α_R, β_R) Euler angles: $(\hat{z}_{MF}, \alpha_R = 90^\circ)$ and (\hat{y}_{RMF}, β_R) (see Figure 1), where the β_R angle is related to the α bending angle of the molecule by:

$$\beta_R = \pi - \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad (3)$$

For the NO_2 molecule in the ground state equilibrium geometry, $\alpha = 134^\circ$ and $\beta_R = 113^\circ$. The R-MFPAD is then described in the RMF by an expression similar to Eq. (1) with no restriction on the values of ν .

Since the orientation of the plane of the molecule is not determined experimentally for a single PI process, the one photon RFPAD corresponds to the average of the R-MFPAD over the azimuthal angle γ_R between the x_{RMF} and x_{RF} axes [17]:

$$T_{fi}^{(LP\ RF)} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} T_{fi}^{(LP\ RMF)} d\gamma_R \quad (4)$$

resulting in non-zero terms only for $\nu = 0$: four $F_{N,0}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions describe the RFPAD in this case [17] where the electron emission direction in the RF is described by the (θ_e, ϕ_e) polar and azimuthal angles.

Turning to multiphoton ionization of a non-linear molecule, assuming that the ionization occurs from a single excited state, the R-MFPAD can be written as a single product of the $T_{n-1,i}^{(n-1,LP)}$ differential cross section describing the $(n-1)$ bound-to-bound transitions between resonant or near

resonant excited states and the $T_{f(n-1)}^{(1,LP)}$ R-MFPAD for the one photon ionization of the excited state populated by absorption of the $(n-1)$ photons:

$$T_{fi}^{(n,LP\ RMF)} = T_{(n-1)i}^{(n-1,LP)} T_{f(n-1)}^{(1,LP)} \quad (5)$$

Following our previous study on ion pair formation induced by multiphoton excitation of the NO_2 molecule [25], $T_{(n-1)i}^{(n-1,LP)}$ corresponds to the product of the one photon excitation probabilities associated to each transition and can be expanded in terms of its azimuthal dependence on the orientation of the plane of the molecule ($\gamma_{LP} - \gamma_R$):

$$T_{(n-1)i}^{(n-1,LP)}(\chi_{LP}, \gamma_{LP} - \gamma_R) = \sum_{v'=-2(n-1)}^{2(n-1)} H_{v'}^{(n-1,LP)}(\chi_{LP}) \exp[-iv'(\gamma_{LP} - \gamma_R)] \quad (6)$$

The multiphoton R-MFPAD can then be expressed as:

$$T_{fi}^{(n,LP\ RMF)}(\theta_e, \phi_e, \chi_{LP}, \gamma_{LP} - \gamma_R) = \text{Re} \left\{ \sum_{v'=-2(n-1)}^{2(n-1)} H_{v'}^{(n-1,LP)}(\chi_{LP}) \exp[-iv'(\gamma_{LP} - \gamma_R)] \right. \\ \left. \times \sum_v \sum_{L=0,2}^L \sum_{N=0}^L F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e) P_L^N(\cos \chi_{LP}) \exp[iN(\phi_e - \gamma_{LP}) + iv(\phi_e - \gamma_R)] \right\} \quad (7)$$

As for the one photon case, the measured multiphoton RFPAD results from the average of the R-MFPAD over γ_R (Eq. (4)) leading here to non zero terms only for $v = v'$. The RFPAD for PI by multiphoton excitation of a non-chiral molecule such as NO_2 , using linearly polarized light is written as:

$$T_{fi}^{(n,LP\ PRF)}(\theta_e, \phi_e, \chi_{LP}, \gamma_{LP}) = \sum_v H_v^{(n-1,LP)}(\chi_{LP}) \times \\ \sum_{L=0,2}^L \sum_{N=0}^L F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e) P_L^N(\cos \chi_{LP}) \cos[(v+N)(\phi_e - \gamma_{LP})] \quad (8)$$

In the following we fix $\gamma_{LP} = 0^\circ$, such that the light polarization axis lies in the x_{RF} - z_{RF} plane and we drop the LP index for convenience.

In the general expression obtained in Eq. (8), the v index of the summation is now limited by one of the two conditions $-2l_{max} \leq (N+v) \leq 2l_{max}$ or $-2(n-1) \leq v \leq 2(n-1)$. For large partial wave expansions, it is limited by the number of photons, with $4(3n-2) F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions being involved in the multiphoton RFPAD. This shows that increasing the number of photons taking part in the excitation process of a given molecular state prior to ionization by the n^{th} photon increases the maximal number of $F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions in the expression of the RFPAD (Eq. (8)), i.e., the accessible information about photoionization of the excited state, the upper limit being the number of $F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ involved in the description of the one photon R-MFPAD for a given l_{max} (Eq. (1)). This results from the alignment of the molecule induced by the absorption of $(n-1)$ photons. In particular, we note that a more extended knowledge about the photoionization of the excited state produced by absorption of the $(n-1)$ photons can be extracted from the multiphoton RFPAD than from a virtual experiment where one photon ionization of randomly oriented excited molecules would be studied via the RFPAD, leading to four $F_{N,0}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions.

For 5 photon excitation of NO_2 , this leads to 52 $F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions if the maximum partial wave is $l_{max} > 3$. For $l_{max} = 3$, 40 $F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions are still involved. Moreover, depending on the bound-to-bound reaction pathways, the $H_v^{(n-1)}(\chi)$ functions may not be linearly independent so that the $F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions cannot be readily extracted from the experimental results.

Therefore, an alternative analysis method has been developed in order to allow for the most tractable comparison between theoretical and experimental results and further to extract the dynamical information on the photoionization process in terms of dipole matrix elements.

3.2. Recoil Frame Azimuthal Harmonics (RFAH)

The analysis method relies on the decomposition of the RFPAD in terms of the $R_K^{(n,\text{RF})}(\chi, \theta_e)$ Recoil Frame Azimuthal Harmonic (RFAH) functions equal to the azimuthal Fourier components in the $\cos[(\nu + N)(\phi_e)]$ expansion, where $K = (N + \nu)$ and $K_{\text{max}} = 2(n-1) + 2 = 2n$. The RFPAD for linearly polarized light can be expanded in the RFAH functions as:

$$T_{fi}^{(n,\text{RF})}(\theta_e, \phi_e, \chi) = \sum_{K=0}^{2n} R_K^{(n,\text{RF})}(\chi, \theta_e) \cos(K\phi_e) \quad (9)$$

with:

$$R_K^{(n,\text{RF})}(\chi, \theta_e) = \sum_{L=0,2}^L \sum_{N=0}^L H_{K-N}^{(n-1)}(\chi) F_{N,K-N}^{(L)}(\theta_e) P_L^N(\cos \chi) \quad (10)$$

The first term independent of the azimuthal angle ϕ_e (zero order in ϕ_e) is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_0(\chi, \theta_e) = & H_0(\chi) F_{0,0}^{(0)}(\theta_e) + H_0(\chi) P_2^0(\cos \chi) F_{0,0}^{(2)}(\theta_e) \\ & + H_{-1}(\chi) P_2^1(\cos \chi) F_{1,-1}^{(2)}(\theta_e) \\ & + H_{-2}(\chi) P_2^2(\cos \chi) F_{2,-2}^{(2)}(\theta_e) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The corresponding expressions describing the other azimuthal harmonics are obtained similarly. We note that the RFAH bidimensional histograms $R_K(\chi, \theta_e)$ of even order K are symmetric with respect to the plane $\chi = 90^\circ$ while those of odd order are antisymmetric.

Each RFAH can then be expanded in terms of products of Legendre polynomials in χ and θ_e :

$$R_K(\chi, \theta_e) = \sum_{L'=K}^{2n} \sum_{L''=K}^{2l_{\text{max}}} D_{L',L''}^{(K)} P_{L'}^K(\cos \chi) P_{L''}^K(\cos \theta_e) \quad (12)$$

where the L' and L'' row and column indexes of the $D^{(K)}$ matrix are associated to the developments in θ_e (limited by $2l_{\text{max}}$) and in χ (limited by $2n$), respectively. The (n,RF) superscript in the RFAH label is omitted for simplicity.

The $D^{(K)}$ matrices provide a complete representation of the multiphoton RFPAD which contains all the dynamical information on the photoionization process. They constitute the building blocks for the extraction of the measured RFAH histograms and subsequent RFPADs for each orientation of the recoil axis with respect to the polarization axis as illustrated in sect. 6. However, in the perspective of a quantitative comparison with theory, a large number of parameters are still involved. For the azimuthal harmonic of zero-order in the development in ϕ_e , the number of non-zero matrix elements in the $D^{(K)}$ matrix is $(n+1)(2l_{\text{max}} + 1)$. For example, for the $n = 5$ photon excitation of NO_2 and $l_{\text{max}} = 4$ this leads to 54 terms.

3.3. Principal component analysis

In order to reduce the number of relevant parameters in the comparison between theory and experiment, we use a principal component analysis method. This multivariate analysis permits the reduction of the number of parameters of each $D^{(K)}$ matrix.

In a first step, the covariance matrix B derived from the $D^{(K)}$ matrix is calculated:

$$B_{L',L''}^{(K)} = \sum_{L'''} D_{L',L'''}^{(K)} D_{L'',L'''}^{(K)} \quad (13)$$

where the order of the matrix for a given value of K is $2n+1-K$. This matrix is then diagonalized by a unitary matrix $U_{L',\lambda}^{(K)}$ with eigenvectors ordered according to the corresponding Λ_λ eigenvalues. The principal components are selected by the magnitude of the eigenvalues relative to the maximum

eigenvalue; typically we include M eigenvectors whose eigenvalues are larger than 0.1% of that corresponding to the main component, where $M < N$.

The dependences on the polar angles χ and θ_e can both be written as expansions on Legendre polynomials, for $\lambda = 1, 2, \dots, M$, according to:

$$J_\lambda^{(K)}(\chi) = \sum_{L'} U_{L',\lambda}^{(K)} P_{L'}^K(\cos \chi) \quad (14)$$

$$G_\lambda^{(K)}(\theta_e) = \sum_{L',L''} U_{L',\lambda}^{(K)} D_{L',L''}^{(K)} P_{L'}^K(\cos \theta_e) \quad (15)$$

The RFPAD can then be reconstructed using the $J_\lambda^{(K)}(\chi)$ and $G_\lambda^{(K)}(\theta_e)$ functions giving

$$T_{fi}^{(n,\text{RF})}(\theta_e, \phi_e, \chi) = \sum_K \sum_{\lambda=1}^M J_\lambda^{(K)}(\chi) G_\lambda^{(K)}(\theta_e) \cos(K\phi_e) \quad (16)$$

This method is applied for the RFPAD analysis in section 6.

4. Theoretical method for PI of NO₂ Rydberg states

The photoionization transition matrix elements were computed using two levels of calculation. First was a method that was very similar to that used in [17], where the calculations were performed using single-channel, single-configuration representations of the photoionized state, in the spirit of the frozen-core Hartree-Fock method [33]. The matrix elements were computed using the ePolyScat code [34,35]. The one-electron molecular orbitals were expanded by using an augmented correlation-consistent polarized valence triple zeta aug-cc-pVTZ basis set [36,37] augmented by diffuse functions to represent the Rydberg orbitals used in the calculations. The additional functions had Gaussians with exponents (angular momentum) of 0.0594 (d), 0.147 (f) on the O atoms, and 0.01141 (s), 0.00589 (s), 0.00209 (s), 0.001016 (s), 0.000387 (s), 0.0167 (p), 0.00813 (p), 0.00273 (p), 0.00106 (p), 0.00031 (p), 0.0419 (d), 0.0289 (d), 0.00846 (d), 0.107 (f), 0.0315 (f), 0.00926 (f) on the central N atom, for a total of 277 basis functions. In all calculations the bond length was held constant at $R(\text{N-O})=1.19455$ Å. The fixed-nuclei (FN) photoionization calculations used a single-center expansion up to $l_{\text{max}}=60$. A set of orbitals were first computed using a restricted HF calculation on the ground state of NO₂. Then the Rydberg orbitals were computed in the field of the ionic ground state where the orbitals were frozen as the original HF orbitals. Given the observed photoelectron energy of 0.5 eV, we considered mainly states which had an IP of ~ 2.6 eV. From our computed energies, which are similar to those found in [38] we selected the $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ states $3p\sigma$, $4s\sigma$, $3p\pi(a_1)$ and $3p\pi(b_1)$. Computed RFPADs were obtained for these states at $\angle\text{ONO}$ of 134° , 150° , 165° , and 175° .

The second set of calculations used correlated target wave functions and included two coupled electronic channels. These calculations were performed using the complex Kohn method [39,40]. The one-electron basis set was the same as in the single-configuration calculations discussed above. The orbitals used to represent the bound molecular orbitals were obtained from a state-averaged complete active space self-consistent field (SA-CASSCF) calculation [41] which included the ground state of NO₂ (X^2A_1), the ground state of NO₂⁺ (X^1A_1), and the first excited state of NO₂⁺ (a^3B_2). The first six orbitals ($1a_1$, $1b_2$, $2a_1$, $2b_2$, $3a_1$, $4a_1$) were doubly occupied in all configurations and there were 11 active electrons for the neutral state or 10 active electrons in the ion state in eight orbitals ($5a_1$, $6a_1$, $7a_1$, $1b_1$, $1a_2$, $2b_1$, $3b_2$, $4b_2$). An additional $5b_2$ orbital, used in the construction of the $3p\sigma$ initial Rydberg state, was computed by adding the $5b_2$ orbital to the active set, adding a 2B_2 state to the state average, but freezing the 14 orbitals obtained in the first SA-CASSCF calculation. In the scattering calculations, the X^1A_1 and a^3B_2 ion states were included. As in the single channel calculations, the photoelectron was taken to have 0.5 eV kinetic energy in the channel leading to the X^1A_1 state of NO₂⁺. The initial state in the photoionization process was the 1B_2 state which had a single electron in the $5b_2$ orbital in its main configuration. When using correlated target states in the scattering calculation, one must choose carefully the penetration terms included in the wave function in order to avoid the appearance of pseudo-resonances. In the present calculation we have used the multiconfiguration-close-coupling approach [42,43] where the penetration terms are taken as the direct product of the weakly occupied orbitals with the linear combination of configuration state functions that define the target states.

5. Experimental results: laboratory frame observables

In this section, we first report the measured energetic observables in terms of the electron-ion kinetic energy correlation diagrams (KECDs) for dissociative ionization processes and photoelectron energy spectra for non-dissociative ionization, for both multiphoton ionization induced by femtosecond pulses at $\lambda = 397$ nm and one-photon ionization at $h\nu = 15.69$ eV corresponding to a five photon excitation energy. The angular distributions of the emitted photoelectrons and photoions with respect to the light polarization axis in the laboratory frame are also reported for the dominant processes identified in both photon excitation modes.

5.1. Energetic observables

5.1.1 Multiphoton ionization induced by femtosecond pulses at $\lambda = 397$ nm

The bidimensional histogram of the (NO^+, e) coincident events following DPI in the form of the electron-ion kinetic energy correlation diagram (KECD) is presented in Figure 2 at $\lambda = 397$ nm linearly polarized light. The applied extraction field of 30V/cm ensured a 4π collection of electrons and ion fragments up to a kinetic energy of 2.5 eV. The abscissa axis represents the kinetic energy release (KER) of the heavy fragments, where

$$KER = E_{\text{NO}^+} + E_{\text{O}} = \left(1 + \frac{m_{\text{NO}^+}}{m_{\text{O}^-}}\right) E_{\text{NO}^+} \quad (17)$$

and the ordinate axis is the photoelectron energy (E_e). Within the assumption that n photons are absorbed, the diagonal lines in the KECD represent the opened dissociation limits characterized by E_D , the potential energy of the fragments choosing as a reference the NO_2 (X^2A_1) neutral ground state at the equilibrium geometry, and ν the NO^+ fragment vibrational level. These quantities obey the following equations:

$$nh\nu - E_D = KER + E_e, \text{ with } E_D = E_{\text{elec}} + E_{\text{int}} \quad (18)$$

where E_e is the electron kinetic energy, E_{elec} is the electronic potential energy of the fragments and E_{int} the internal ro-vibrational energy of the NO^+ fragment. The E_D values for the lowest dissociation limits of NO_2^+ are reported in Table 1.

Figure 2 : Electron-Ion Kinetic Energy Correlation Diagram for (NO^+, e) events from MPI of NO_2 at $\lambda = 397$ nm using a 30 V/cm extraction field. The $L_1[5]$, $L_2[5]$ and $L_1[4]$ continuous lines represent the ground state (index 1) and first excited state (index 2) dissociation limits, assuming absorption of 5 or 4 photons, respectively (see text). The dashed lines feature the position of these limits when vibrational excitation of the NO^+ fragment occurs, as labeled by ν . The insert represents a zoom of the corner of the KECD corresponding to low KER and E_e , as measured at $\lambda = 395$ nm with a low extraction field of 5 V/cm.

We label $L_1[5]$ and $L_2[5]$ the straight lines corresponding to the population of the $\{\text{NO}^+ (X^1\Sigma^+, \nu = 0) + \text{O} (^3P)\}$ and $\{\text{NO}^+ (X^1\Sigma^+, \nu = 0) + \text{O} (^1D)\}$ first and second dissociation limits lying at 12.38 eV and 14.35 eV (Table 1), respectively, assuming absorption of $n = 5$ photons. The $L_1[4]$ line

features the ground state dissociation limit at 12.38 eV for the absorption of $n = 4$ photons which lies in the corner of the KECD corresponding to low KER and E_e values, as shown in the insert of Figure 2.

Limit	Products	E_D (eV)
L ₁	O(³ P) + NO ⁺ (X ¹ Σ ⁺ , $\nu=0$)	12.38
	O(³ P) + NO ⁺ (X ¹ Σ ⁺ , $\nu=1$)	12.67
	O(³ P) + NO ⁺ (X ¹ Σ ⁺ , $\nu=2$)	12.96
L ₂	O(¹ D) + NO ⁺ (X ¹ Σ ⁺ , $\nu=0$)	14.35

Table 1 : Lowest dissociation limits of the NO₂⁺ ion and corresponding potential energy of the fragments.

Most of the structures observed in the KECD (Figure 2) require the absorption of five photons. The dominant MPDI process, labeled process A, is characterized by a maximum electron energy $E_e \approx 0.45$ eV and an extended KER distribution of the NO⁺ fragments localized between the L₂[5] and L₁[5] limits, demonstrating a remarkable ro-vibrational excitation of the ion fragment. Two sub-structures are resolved and assigned to the population of two series of ro-vibrational states of the NO⁺ (X¹Σ⁺, ν) molecular fragment: $\nu = 0,1,2$ with a maximum for $\nu = 1$ (KER ≈ 2.6 eV; $E_e \approx 0.4$ eV), and $\nu = 3-6$ with a maximum for $\nu = 3-4$ (KER ≈ 1.6 eV; $E_e \approx 0.46$ eV), labeled A,1 and A,3-6 in Table 2. The ion-fragment energy resolution does not allow for resolution of the ro-vibrational states.

Besides the composite process A, a weaker and more localized structure B is observed characterized by the (KER ≈ 1.2 eV; $E_e = 1.6$ eV) correlated energies, centered about the {NO⁺ (X¹Σ⁺, $\nu \approx 1$) + O(³P)} dissociation limit.

The ridge D, elongated along the L₁[4] {NO⁺(X¹Σ⁺, $\nu = 0$) + O(³P)} ground state dissociation limit at low E_e and KER, can be attributed to a four-photon reaction. The insert of Figure 2 corresponds to the KECD zoomed on this process measured at $\lambda = 395$ nm with a low extraction field of 5 V/cm.

Comparing the KECDs measured in the 397-405 nm wavelength range explored, the main characteristics of processes A and B are quite similar, however the electron-ion energy sharing of the additional photon excitation energy depends on the MPDI process. Although the total excitation energy of five photons increases by 0.31 eV when varying the wavelength from 405 to 397 nm, the E_e electron energy at the maximum of peaks A and B varies by about 0.1 eV, i.e. close to the energy shift of one (or two) photon, while the KER distribution is shifted by about one vibrational level of the NO⁺ fragment, the 0.2 eV excess energy being released into internal energy of the NO⁺ (X¹Σ⁺) molecular fragment. The observation is different for process (D) where the E_e electron energy varies exactly as the four-photon total excitation energy in the explored 400 nm-395 nm wavelength range, where it is observable.

Figure 3 displays the associated 1D photoelectron energy spectra, both for the (NO⁺, e) DPI events discussed in the KECD and the (NO₂⁺, e) coincident events for non-dissociative MPI reactions at the same excitation wavelength. We use the symbols A, B and D to label the peaks in the (NO⁺, e) 1D photoelectron spectrum consistent with the assignments in the KECD, and δ ($E_e \approx 0.15$ eV), α ($E_e \approx 0.45$ eV), γ ($E_e \approx 0.65$ eV), and β ($E_e \approx 1.6$ eV) the peaks in the (NO₂⁺, e) PE spectrum found at very similar positions.

Figure 3 : Photoelectron spectrum for MPDI (black full line) and MPI (blue dotted line) measured for excitation at $\lambda = 397$ nm, using a 30 V/cm extraction field, reflecting relative intensities for dissociative and non-dissociative ionization.

As observed for MPDI processes A and B (NO^+ , e), the energy shift of the four peaks α - γ , when the wavelength varies from $\lambda = 405$ nm to $\lambda = 397$ nm is of the order of 0.1 eV, i.e. an energy shift corresponding to that of one photon, the excess energy being transferred into internal energy of the ionic state. Table 2 displays the relative BRs for the peaks assigned in Figure 3. The relative probability of MPDI at 397 nm is about 70% of the PI events leading to dissociation into ($\text{NO}^+ + \text{O}$).

The dominant peak at $E_e \approx 0.45$ eV in the MPDI photoelectron spectrum is broader than the one seen for non-dissociative MPI: its asymmetric shape results from the superposition of the peak associated with the 2-2.6 eV KER region with a maximum at 0.4 eV (A,1) and the broader component associated with the 1-2 eV KERs (A,3-6) with a maximum at 0.46 eV and a secondary bump at 0.65 eV, quasi resonant with peak γ in the MPI PE spectrum, as extrapolated from the KECD. The two main structures at 0.4 and 0.45 eV observed in the PE spectrum for MPDI can be attributed to the vibrational excitation of $\text{NO}_2^+(X^1\Sigma_g^+)$ in the bending mode while the secondary bump at 0.65 eV, can be assigned to the stretching vibrational mode. The secondary peak at $E_e \approx 1.55$ eV is also narrower for MPI than for MPDI.

Process	(KER, E_e) ± 0.05 eV	Dissociation limit (v_{NO^+})	BR ($\pm 1\%$) 397 nm	$\beta_e (\pm 0.1)$			$\beta_i (\pm 0.1)$		
				β_2	β_4	β_6	β_2	β_4	β_6
A, 1	(1.2, 0.4) ⁽¹⁾	$L_1[5], v=1$	14	0.9	0	0	2.9	1.4	0
A, 3-6	(2.4, 0.45) ⁽¹⁾	$L_1[5], v=3-6$	30	0.9	0	0	2.6	1.0	0
B	(1.1, 1.5) ⁽¹⁾	$L_1[5], v=1$	10	1.0	0	0	2.6	1.0	0.2
δ	(0, 0.1) ⁽¹⁾	ND	3	--	--	--	--	--	--
α	(0, 0.45) ⁽¹⁾	ND	11	0.3	0.1	0	--	--	--
γ	(0, 0.65) ⁽¹⁾	ND	5	--	--	--	--	--	--
β	(0, 1.55) ⁽¹⁾	ND	7	1.4	0.8	0.5	--	--	--

Table 2 : Dissociation limits, branching ratios and asymmetry parameters characterizing the angular distribution in the laboratory frame for electrons and ions, for the main MPDI processes (A and B) and MPI processes (α , β , γ , δ) at $\lambda = 397$ nm.

If the dissociation limits are well identified for the MPDI processes, as well as the number of absorbed photons, the photoelectron energies corresponding to the main peaks, as well as their energy width, do not point to photoionization processes into known excited states of the NO_2^+ ion according to vertical transitions in the Franck Condon region associated to the $\text{NO}_2(X^2A_1)$ ground state geometry. These results demonstrate that significant nuclear dynamics takes place during the 70 fs pulse duration. Since ionization into the $\text{NO}_2^+(X^1\Sigma_g^+)$ ground state is the only open channel after 4 photon absorption (excitation energy of 12.49 eV), one expects that the peaks in the photoelectron spectrum for MPI pertain to this process.

5.1.2 Single Photon ionization at $h\nu = 15.69$ eV

The KECD associated to (NO^+, e) events for single-photon ionization at $h\nu \approx 15.69$ eV presented in Figure 4 is drastically different from the one measured for multiphoton ionization for a same total photon excitation energy. Five structures are resolved and labeled in Roman numerals (I-V), processes I and II being dominant.

Figure 4 : Electron-Ion Kinetic Energy Correlation Diagram for (NO^+, e) events from single photon excitation of NO_2 at $h\nu = 15.69$ eV using a 60 V/cm extraction field.

Diagonal lines identifying the open dissociation limits are positioned onto the KECD according to Eq. (18). The two opened dissociation limits $\{\text{NO}^+(X^1\Sigma^+) + \text{O}(^3\text{P})\}$ (L_1) and $\{\text{NO}^+(X^1\Sigma^+) + \text{O}(^1\text{D})\}$ (L_2) are populated, the ground state limit being preferred. It is remarkable that SPDI under such conditions produces the molecular fragment mainly in the $\nu = 0$ lowest vibrational level, meaning that no energy transfer into the internal degrees of the molecular fragments is observed contrary to the multiphoton excitation MPDI (Figure 2).

The E_e electron energy positions for the peaks observed fit very well those assigned in high resolution photoelectron spectroscopy of NO_2^+ and they allow an unambiguous identification of the populated molecular ionic states [44]. Figure 5 displays the E_e electron energy distribution corresponding to the (NO^+, e) SPDI events at $h\nu \approx 15.69$ eV, which is the projection of the KECD onto the E_e axis. The peaks resolved for the one-photon SPDI reactions correspond to the population of the $(B^1B_2, A^1A_2, b^3A_2, a^3B_2)$ NO_2^+ electronic states, as shown, based on the previous assignments [44,45].

Table 3 displays the five identified SPDI processes I-V, characterized by the (KER, E_e) values at the maximum of each peak in the KECD, as well as their relative branching ratios. The relevant RFPADs for the SPDI processes at 15.69 eV will be discussed elsewhere: those characterizing the dominant process I leading to the $\text{NO}_2^+(b^3A_2)$ ionic state have been reported earlier for $h\nu = 14.4$ eV [17]. Figure 5 also includes the photoelectron spectrum measured for non-dissociative photoionization induced by single photon excitation at $h\nu \approx 15.69$ eV. The peaks resolved for the non-dissociative SPI channels characterize the population of the a^3B_2 and $X^1\Sigma_g^+$ NO_2^+ electronic states, and to a minor extent the $\text{NO}_2^+(A^1A_2)$ state, consistent with the FC factors [44]: the relative branching ratios and photoelectron asymmetry parameters for these two processes are displayed in Table 3.

Figure 5 : Photoelectron spectrum for non dissociative SPI events (blue dotted line) and SPDI events (black full line) for single photon excitation of NO_2 at $h\nu = 15.69$ eV using a 60 V/cm extraction field. The corresponding binding energy (BE) is also indicated.

Process	(KER, E_e) (eV) ± 0.05	NO_2^+ state (v_1, v_2, v_3)	Dissociation limit (v_{NO^+})	BR ($\pm 1\%$)	β_e ± 0.1	β_{NO^+} ± 0.1
II	(0.7, 2.6)	a^3B_2 (040)	$L_1, v=0$	12	-0.6	0.1
I	(1.1, 2.1)	b^3A_2 (000)	$L_1, v=0$	21	-0.3	0.0
III	(1.4, 1.6)	A^1A_2 (010)	$L_1, v=1, 2$	5	-0.2	0.1
IV	(2.15, 1.2)	B^1B_2 (010)	$L_1, v=0, 1, 2$	9	-0.2	0.3
V	(0.2, 1.2)	B^1B_2 (010)	$L_2, v=0$	6	-0.2	-0.2
NDPI	(0, 4.60)	$X^1\Sigma_g^+$	ND	25	+0.3	--
NDPI	(0, 2.90)	a^3B_2 (000)	ND	11	-0.3	--
NDPI	(0, 1.7)	A^1A_2 (000)	ND	1	--	--

Table 3 : Dissociation limit, branching ratio and asymmetry parameters characterizing the angular distribution in the laboratory frame for electrons and ions, for SPDI and SPI processes at $h\nu = 15.69$ eV using a 60 V/cm extraction field.

These single photon results confirm that the deviation of the photoionization processes observed in multiphoton excitation of the NO_2 molecule from the prediction of vertical transitions at the ground state equilibrium geometry is not due to the presence of a resonant state at the 15.69 eV total photon excitation energy. Even for the processes B in MPDI and β in MPI which might be tentatively attributed to the population of the $\text{NO}_2^+(A^1A_2)$ ionic state in the FC region after absorption of 5 photons, by analogy with the SPI observations, the E_e variation when varying the laser wavelength does not support the interpretation of this peak as due to a direct photoionization reaction. One has then to invoke reaction pathways which imply a significant change of the NO_2 geometry from the equilibrium initial state, taking place during the 70 fs duration of the light pulse at lower photon excitation energies than that corresponding to the total photon excitation energy.

5.2 Laboratory frame photoemission for MPI and MPDI processes

For multiphoton ionization involving n absorbed photons, the angular distribution of emitted photoelectrons or ion fragments with respect to the light polarization axis, characterized by β_{2k} asymmetry parameters, expands in terms of Legendre polynomials a priori up to order $2n$, as:

$$H(\chi) \propto 1 + \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_{2k} P_{2k}(\cos \chi) \quad (19)$$

The β_{NO^+} asymmetry parameters according to Eq. (19) characterizing processes A and B (MPDI) as well as the β_e asymmetry parameters for processes A, B (MPDI) and α and β (MPI) are displayed in

Table 2. The PE angular distributions for processes characterized by comparable E_e energies in MPDI and non-dissociative MPI are markedly different. The PE angular distributions for peak A in MPDI and peak α in MPI are characterized by a single β_e asymmetry parameter, however the absolute values amount to $\beta_e \approx 1$ (A) and $\beta_e \approx 0.3$ (α), respectively. On the other hand, the PE angular distribution for peak B in MPDI described by a single $\beta_e \approx 1$ parameter contrasts with that of peak β in MPI described by a set of three parameters $\beta_2 \approx 1.4$, $\beta_4 \approx 0.8$, $\beta_6 \approx 0.5$.

For MPDI A and B processes, the ion angular distribution strongly aligned along the light polarization axis involves two or three β_{NO^+} asymmetry parameters, consistent with the absorption of at least three photons prior to dissociation. Photodissociation induced by multiphoton excitation of the NO_2 C_{2v} molecule, involving one-photon transitions via near-resonant intermediate states, have been modeled in the previously reported study of $(\text{NO}^+, \text{O}^-)$ ion pair formation [25] at 400 nm. Four types of bound-to-bound transitions have been considered: type-1 corresponding to a transition moment in the molecular frame perpendicular to the plane of the NO_2 molecule (\mathbf{t}_1), type-2 where the transition moment lies parallel to the O-O axis (\mathbf{t}_2), type-3 associated with a transition moment parallel to the C_{2v} principal symmetry axis (\mathbf{t}_3) and finally type-4, corresponds to a transition parallel to the recoil axis, which is possible when the asymmetric stretching mode of the molecule is excited (\mathbf{t}_4). The reaction pathway labeled [2,2,2,2] corresponds to four bound-to-bound parallel transitions (\mathbf{t}_2) between states of A_1 and B_2 symmetry, where the molecule remains in a C_{2v} bent geometry.

For a MPDI process, the angular distribution of the NO^+ ions results from the $(n-1)$ bound-to-bound transitions between valence states plus the photoionization reaction from an excited state. In Figure 6 the measured NO^+ ion fragment angular distribution for the dominant MPDI process A is compared to two model angular distributions labeled [2,2,2,2]-2 and [2,2,2,2]-3, which involve a [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound reaction pathway at the equilibrium geometry and a PI reaction described by a type-2 or a type-3 transition. We observe a quite good agreement with the [2,2,2,2]-2 model distribution, very close to the [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound angular profile.

Figure 6 : Ion fragment angular distributions for MPDI process A at 397 nm: experimental data (dots and fit black line) compared to model angular distributions for selected five-photon excitation pathways labeled [2,2,2,2]-2 (red full line) and [2,2,2,2]-3 (red dotted line) at the ground state equilibrium geometry (see text).

Despite the lower angular resolution achieved when the measured distribution relies on the detection of a single ion fragment, instead of two in the ion pair process [25], the asymmetry parameters characterizing processes A and B are found to be very similar to those measured in ion pair formation induced by 4 photon excitation at the same wavelength (not shown here), suggesting a similar reaction pathway for the bound-to-bound part of the reaction, as well as a PI reaction close to a type-2 “parallel” transition. The deviations observed between the two distributions can then be

attributed to the photoionization reaction, which weakly contributes to the ion fragment anisotropy in this case. We note that, as described in [25], the $H(\chi)$ distribution characterizing a [2,2,2,2] angular profile is very close to that corresponding e.g. to a transition noted [2,2,2p-5] involving two type-2 one photon transitions and one two-photon transition between the $\text{NO}_2(\text{A}^2\text{B}_2)$ first excited state of NO_2 and the $5\text{A}'$ excited state strongly mixed with the $3\text{p}\sigma(\text{B}_2)$ member of the $\text{R}^*[(6\text{a}_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg series converging to the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{XA}_1)$ ionic ground state (see sect. 8).

6. Multiphoton induced RFPADs: experimental results compared with model calculations

6.1 Recoil Frame Photoelectron Angular Distributions

This section is devoted to the analysis of the measured RFPADs according to the different steps of the method proposed in sect. 3 based on the expansion of the RFPAD in terms of the $R_K^{(n,LP,RF)}(\chi_{\text{LP}}, \theta_e)$ recoil frame azimuthal harmonics (RFAH) (Eq.[9]). These results are compared with computed observables based on the one-channel and two-channel calculations performed for photoionization of the $\text{R}[(6\text{a}_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states converging to the ground state of the ion, as described in sect. 4. In order to facilitate this comparison, the experimental and theoretical data are normalized to the same total photoionization cross section. For a 5 photon process and $l_{\text{max}} > 3$ the RFPAD can be expanded in terms of up to 10 RFAHs functions. For sake of simplicity, we restrict here the presentation of the data to the discussion of the two RFAH histograms corresponding to the zero and first orders in $\cos[(\nu + N)(\phi_e)]$ and we note that the contribution of RFAHs of higher order significantly decreases with increasing K.

Figure 7 (a, b, c) represent the bidimensional histograms corresponding to the $R_0(\chi, \theta_e)$ zero-order azimuthal harmonic measured for the MPDI process A by excitation at 397 nm wavelength compared to that deduced from the computed RFPAD for photoionization of the $3\text{p}\sigma$ Rydberg state, for a [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound reaction pathway keeping the NO_2 molecule at the equilibrium geometry, for the one-channel and the two-channel calculations. This state was selected among the computed Rydberg states for this comparison because of its b_2 symmetry character fitting well with the considered pathway. The three diagrams, symmetric with respect to the $\chi \sim 90^\circ$ axis (see sect. 3.2), show intensity maxima for an ion recoil direction parallel to the polarization axis ($\chi \sim 0^\circ$ and 180°). The projection of the histogram onto the abscissa axis corresponding to the integration of the multiphoton RFPAD over (θ_e, ϕ_e) polar and azimuthal PE angles represents the angular distribution of the ion fragments in the laboratory frame displayed in Figure 6. As discussed in sect. 5.2, it is well described by a [2,2,2,2]-2 reaction involving a [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound reaction pathway which induces alignment of the excited molecules and a PI reaction also described by a type-2 parallel transition. We note that the computed ion fragment angular distribution for a [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound reaction pathway followed by photoionization of the $3\text{p}\sigma$ Rydberg state is rather close to the [2,2,2,2]-2 angular profile.

A strong FW-BW asymmetry reflecting the favored photoelectron emission in the direction of the recoil ion ($\theta_e \sim 0^\circ$) is observed experimentally. This anisotropy is well predicted by the calculation, being more pronounced in the one-channel case. However, the corresponding computed RFAH presents two other intensity maxima at $\theta_e \sim 70^\circ$ and $\theta_e \sim 140^\circ$, which are not observed experimentally: the smooth behavior of the two-channel calculation is in better agreement with the experiment in this θ_e range.

Figure 7 : RFAH functions $R_0(\chi, \theta_e)$ ((a), (b) and (c)) and $R_1(\chi, \theta_e)$ ((d), (e) and (f)) measured for the MPDI process A at $\lambda = 397$ nm ((a) and (d)) and computed for photoionization of the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state converging to the NO_2^+ ground state, at the NO_2 equilibrium geometry for a $[2,2,2,2]$ bound-to-bound reaction pathway for the one-channel ((b) and (e)) and the two-channel ((c) and (f)) calculations.

The $R_1(\chi, \theta_e)$ first order RFAHs reported in Figure 7 (d, e, f), antisymmetric with respect to the $\chi \sim 90^\circ$ axis (see sect. 3.2), display clear oscillatory structures. Comparing the measured and computed histograms shows that the two-channel calculation is in better agreement with the experiment.

Based on the development of the multiphoton RFPAD in terms of RFAH functions (Eq.[9]), measured and computed RFPADs for selected orientations χ of the NO^+ recoil axis with respect to the polarization direction, e.g., $\chi = 0^\circ$, $\chi = 20^\circ$ and $\chi = 45^\circ$, are reported in Figure 8. Cuts of these RFPADs shown in Figure 9 for $\chi = 0^\circ$ and $\chi = 45^\circ$, $\phi_e = 0^\circ/180^\circ$ and $\phi_e = 90^\circ/270^\circ$ illustrate further the main characteristics of the emission patterns. Consistent with the $R_0(\chi, \theta_e)$ RFAHs, the $\chi = 0^\circ$ measured RFPAD displays a significant FW-BW asymmetry with electron emission favored in the direction of the recoil ion, quite similar to that reported for multiphoton ionization of NO_2 induced at different wavelength [23,24]. The FW-BW asymmetry is well predicted by the one-channel calculation and to a lesser extent by the two-channel calculation, however the two lobes with maxima close to $\theta_e \sim 30^\circ$ observed in the experiment are not found in the calculation. We note that only two $F_{N,v}^{(L)}(\theta_e)$ functions are required to describe the $\chi_i = 0^\circ$ RFPAD (Figure 8 (a,d,g)), since its expression reduces to $I_\chi(\theta_e) = H_0(\chi)(F_{0,0}^{(0)}(\theta_e) + F_{0,0}^{(2)}(\theta_e))$. Additional differences between measured and computed RFPADs are observed especially at $\chi = 20^\circ$ and $\chi = 45^\circ$ where the one-channel computed RFPAD predicts three about equally favored photoemission directions for $\theta_e \sim 10^\circ$, $\phi_e = 0^\circ$ $\theta_e \sim 60^\circ$, $\phi_e = 180^\circ$ and $\theta_e \sim 135^\circ$, $\phi_e = 180^\circ$, the latter two being absent in the measured RFPAD, consistent with the differences observed in the first order RFAH functions.

Figure 8 : RFPADs measured (a-c) for the MPDI process A induced by 5 photon absorption at $\lambda = 397$ nm using linearly polarized light; computed for the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state PI at the equilibrium geometry of the molecule (NO_2 (X^2A_1), $r = 1.2 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = 134^\circ$) using the one-channel (d-f) or the two-channel (g-i) calculation for a [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound reaction pathway; for different orientations of the NO^+ recoil axis with respect to the polarization direction defined by χ : $\chi = 0^\circ$ (a,d,g), $\chi = 20^\circ$ (b,e,h) and $\chi = 45^\circ$ (c,f,i). The polarization axis is contained in the ($z_{\text{RF}}, x_{\text{RF}}$) plan ($\chi_{\text{P}} = 0^\circ$).

Figure 9 : Measured (red solid line) and computed using the one-channel calculation (red dotted line) $I(\theta_e)$ cuts of the RFPADs shown in Figure 8 (a-d) for selected values of χ , and ϕ_e .

6. 2 Principal component analysis of the RFPAD

The principal component analysis allows for an efficient quantitative comparison between experimental and theoretical results. Figure 10 presents the $J(\chi)$ and $G(\theta_e)$ principal components which account for the essential information extracted from the measured and computed $R_0(\chi, \theta_e)$ and $R_1(\chi, \theta_e)$. The very good agreement observed between theoretical and experimental $J(\chi)$ functions supports the proposed description of the MPDI process, in particular the role of a [2,2,2,2] (or [2,2,2p-5])

bound-to-bound reaction pathway. The measured and computed $G_0^I(\theta_e)$ and $G_0^{II}(\theta_e)$ principal components associated with $R_0(\chi, \theta_e)$ present a similar shape: the measured FW-BW asymmetry of electron emission in the RF is better described in the one-channel calculation while its smooth character is closer to the two-channel calculation. The $G_1^I(\theta_e)$ principal component obtained from the measured $R_1(\chi, \theta_e)$ is rather consistent with the result of the two-channel calculation.

Figure 10 : Principal components $J_0^I(\chi)$ and $J_0^{II}(\chi)$ (a), $J_1^I(\chi)$ (b), $G_0^I(\theta_e)$ and $G_0^{II}(\theta_e)$ (c), $G_1^I(\theta_e)$ (d), resulting from the analysis of the $R_0(\chi, \theta_e)$ (a,b,c) and $R_1(\chi, \theta_e)$ (d,e,f) RFAHs corresponding to experimental results (full line) and to the one-channel (dotted line) and two-channel calculations (dashed line) shown in Figure 7. The first components (I) are represented by a blue line, the second ones (II) by a red line. The computed data were obtained at a bond angle of 134° .

7. Relationship between RFPAD and MFPAD: origin of the FW-BW asymmetry

In order to elucidate the possible origin of the observed FW-BW asymmetry in the RFPAD, the relationship between the one photon MFPAD corresponding to the excited state PI and the RFPAD is illustrated here using the one-channel calculation performed for the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state PI at the equilibrium geometry of the molecule (NO_2 (X^2A_1), $r = 1.2 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = 134^\circ$) induced by one photon excitation using linearly polarized light. Figure 11 presents the MFPAD computed for the four orientations of the polarization axis with respect to the symmetry axis z_{MF} most relevant for the present discussion.

Figure 11 : MFPADs computed for the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state one photon ionization at the equilibrium geometry of the molecule for linearly polarized light for four orientations of the polarization axis with respect to the symmetry axis z_{MF} direction defined by (χ_{LP}, γ_{LP}) corresponding to type-3 (a), type-1 (b), type-2 (c) and type-4 (d) transition moment.

For a polarization axis parallel to the symmetry axis z_{MF} (Figure 11 (a)), the MFPAD corresponds to a type-3 transition moment from the $3p\sigma(b_2)$ molecular orbital, into the ionization continua of kb_2 symmetry. Likewise, for a transition moment parallel to the x_{MF} and y_{MF} axis (type-1 and type-2, respectively), the MFPADs correspond to the transitions: $3p\sigma(b_2) \rightarrow ka_2$ and $3p\sigma(b_2) \rightarrow ka_1$, respectively (Figure 11 (b) and Figure 11 (c)). The calculation shows that for PI of the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state the type-2 transition is by far the most probable. Finally, Figure 11 (d) shows the MFPAD for a polarization axis parallel to the NO bond (type-4) which corresponds to the recoil ion direction z_{RF} in the axial recoil approximation, when dissociative ionization occurs. At the equilibrium geometry, and even more strongly for NO_2 geometries characterized by larger bending angles, the type-4 transition is close to the dominant $3p\sigma(b_2) \rightarrow ka_1$ transition.

Figure 12 (a) shows the corresponding R-MFPAD (as defined in sect.3) resulting from the rotation of the MFPAD shown in Figure 11 (d), into the RMF using the Euler angles $\alpha_R = 90^\circ$ and $\beta_R = 113^\circ$. The result of the integration over the γ_R Euler angle (Eq. (4)), reflecting the average over the orientation of the plane of the molecule corresponds to the RFPAD shown in Figure 12 (b). The corresponding multiphoton RFPAD for a considered $[2,2,2,2]$ reaction pathway is shown in Figure 8 (d) in sect. 6.1. The FW-BW asymmetry is therefore attributed to the lobe aligned quasi parallel to the y_{MF} axis in the MFPAD corresponding to a type-2 or a type-4 transition.

Figure 12 : (a) R-MFPAD computed for a polarization axis parallel to the recoil axis as displayed in Figure 11 (d) plotted in the RMF frame deduced from the molecular frame through Euler rotation (\hat{z}_{MF} , $\alpha_R = 90^\circ$) and (\hat{y}_{RMF} , β_R); (b) RFPAD obtained after integration of the R-MFPAD over the γ_R angle about the recoil axis direction.

As described in sect. 4, the fixed-nuclei photoionization calculations reported here for PI of the $R[(6a_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg series used a single-center expansion involving a number of partial waves up to $l_{max}=60$. In order to identify the contribution responsible for the essential characteristics of the measured RFPAD in terms of dipole matrix elements, the calculations have been performed with a strongly reduced number of partial waves. This investigation shows that the main features of the RFPADs computed for the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state, as illustrated in Figure 8 (d-e-f), are well described

when the dipole matrix elements for $l=2$ and $l=3$ are included in the calculation, reflecting the role of $n\delta\sigma$, $\delta(a_1)$ and $n\pi(a_1)$ partial waves in the production of the FW-BW asymmetry.

8. Discussion of possible Reaction Pathways

In this section we discuss possible reaction pathways for MPDI and MPI reactions induced by 397 nm femtosecond pulses, accounting for most of the experimental results presented above, as well as the comparison between experimental and theoretical results. Based on the similarity observed between the PES spectra measured for both MPDI and non dissociative MPI we consider here the assumption of a reaction pathway in two steps, namely photoionization into the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+)$ ground state induced after four photon absorption, followed by one photon induced dissociation of one part of the NO_2^+ ionized population leading to MPDI, as schematized in Figure 13. Moreover, the similarity observed between the reported MPDI ion fragment angular distributions and that of ion pair formation [25] supports a common bound-to-bound reaction pathway for these two processes. Accordingly, the transition may consist of a [2,2,2] or a [2,2p-5] three 400 nm photon absorption from the $\text{NO}_2(\text{X}^2\text{A}_1)$ ground state, bringing the molecule into a region where valence states are strongly mixed with Rydberg series $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ converging to the ground state of the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+)$ ion [25,38,46], such as the $5A'$ excited state lying at a total excitation energy of about 9.3 eV strongly mixed with the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state. Single photon absorption would then ionize such Rydberg states into the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+)$ state vibrationally excited leading to the resolved peaks observed in the PES, through direct ionization or resonant autoionization involving $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states.

The dominant processes A (MPDI) and α (MPI) characterized by a PE energy of ~ 0.45 eV can be assigned to a selective ionization process into $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu)$ highly vibrational states lying at binding energies E_B about 12 eV. Vibrationally selective resonances in PES spectra have been previously observed in femtosecond multiphoton excitation of polyatomic molecules and identified as fingerprints of the role of Rydberg states, firstly by Weber and coworkers in phenol [47,48], then e.g., by Blanchet *et al* in azulene [49] or Hemberger *et al* in cyclopropenylidene [50]. The mechanism proposed by Weber *et al* [47] consists of a multiphoton absorption leading the molecule into an excited valence state. A set of vibrationally excited molecular Rydberg states is then populated by ultrafast internal conversion and ionized by a single photon excitation. Potential surfaces of the Rydberg states closely resemble that of the molecular ion to which they converge, implying that vibration quantum numbers are conserved during ionization: resolved peaks observed by PES are therefore assigned to the different Rydberg series. This scheme is consistent with the PE energy of A or α peaks (Figure 3), since the $E_e \sim 0.45$ eV measured values are very close to the difference between the one photon energy $h\nu \sim 3.1$ eV and the energy gap between the vibrationless (000) origins of the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+)$ ionic (9.586 eV) and $3p\sigma$ Rydberg (6.9 eV) states [51–53]. Considering an effective quantum number $n^* = (n - \delta)$, where n and δ are the principal quantum number and quantum defect characterizing a Rydberg state, associated to each PE energy as proposed by Weber *et al*, a similar $3p\sigma$ (or $3s\sigma$) assignment is obtained for $E_e \approx 0.45$ eV, with $n^* \sim 2.28$ and $\delta \sim 0.71$ according to the equation:

$$h\nu - E_e = \frac{R}{(n - \delta)^2} \quad (20)$$

where R represents the Rydberg constant. According to this analysis, the secondary peak at $E_e \approx 1.65$ eV with a quantum defect of $\delta \sim 0.1$ could be tentatively assigned to a $3d\sigma$ state.

The ionization continuum around 12.4 eV is structured by $[\text{R}^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ autoionizing Rydberg states, converging to the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{a}^3\text{B}_2)$ first excited state [26]. Resonantly excited after absorption of the fourth 400 nm photon, these Rydberg states can themselves be coupled to the vibrationally excited $[\text{R}^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states [26]. Such complex vibronic couplings are likely to induce autoionization into the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3)$ molecular states with vibrational probability distributions corresponding to different geometries, e.g., linear and bent, involving population of stretching and bending vibrational levels which are known to be closely spaced in the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3)$ state [44].

Absorption of a fifth 397 nm photon by the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{X}^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3)$ ground state raises the system into an upper excited state such as the $\text{NO}_2^+(\text{B}^1\text{B}_2)$ state which dissociates into both the L_1 and L_2 limits with a dominant probability for the L_1 ground state limit as observed in Figure 3 and reported

earlier [45], which may account for the observed MPDI. We note that the correlation between the NO_2^+ (B^1B_2) state and the L_1 dissociation limit involves a spin-orbit coupling. The extensive vibrational excitation of the NO^+ fragments can be partly attributed to the energy release associated with the lengthening of the NO bond. In the NO^+ molecule, the energy difference between a bond length of 1.19455 Å, which is the equilibrium value in NO_2 , and 1.06322 Å, which is the equilibrium bond length for NO^+ , is 1.34 eV, which corresponds to an excitation of $\nu = 4$.

Figure 13 : Energy levels of NO_2 ground state and NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$), (a^3B_2) and (B^1B_2). $[R^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ and $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ Rydberg series converging to NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) and NO_2^+ (a^3B_2) states, respectively are represented. The reaction mechanism proposed in sect. 8 is schematized here: red arrows represent 397 nm photon absorption and the blue arrow represent the photoelectron emission. The first ($\text{NO}^+ + \text{O}$) and ($\text{NO}^+ + \text{O}^-$) dissociation limits, as well as the Franck-Condon regions (FC) associated to the ground state of the molecule NO_2 (2A_1) (grey rectangles) are also represented.

Regarding the photoelectron angular distributions, processes A and α are described by a single asymmetry parameter, $\beta_e \sim 0.9$ (MPDI) and 0.3 (MPI), respectively. The difference between the β_e asymmetry parameters measured for A and α can then be attributed to the selectivity of the dissociation process based on the FC factors between the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+$) and (B^1B_2) bent states, as discussed below.

In our previous study of the role of $[R^*(4b_2)^{-1}]$ Rydberg states in one photon ionization of NO_2 in an excitation region around 12.4 eV, we highlighted the dependence of the β_e asymmetry parameter values, typically between 0.3 and 1, as a function of the PE energy, associated with different

geometries of the molecule characterized by the bending angle [26]. In such a scheme, taking into account the bent geometry of NO_2^+ excited states, such as NO_2^+ (B^1B_2), photodissociation would be favored for the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3$) state population at bent geometries. This proposed reaction pathway is supported by the observed peaks in the PE spectrum measured for MPI events, assigned to symmetric stretching vibrational levels, and by the additional contribution of bending vibrational levels observed in the PE spectrum for MPDI events. It is noteworthy that β_e asymmetry parameters obtained in the one-channel and two-channel calculations are very different, and vary in opposite direction as a function of the bending angle as shown in Table 4.

Bond angle (deg)	β_{e2} (1-ch)	β_{e4} (1-ch)	β_{e2} (2-ch)	β_{e4} (2-ch)
134	0.0426	0.6614	1.028	0.1606
150	0.1418	0.3793	0.5203	0.0372
160			-0.235	0.0857
165	1.1421	0.3378		
170			-0.502	0.0691
175	1.3515	0.3625		

Table 4 : Computed electron asymmetry parameters of second and fourth order for PI of the $3p\sigma$ Rydberg state assuming a PE energy $E_e = 0.5$ eV and a [2,2,2,2] bound-to-bound reaction pathway, as a function of the bond angle of the NO_2 molecule, obtained in the one-channel and two-channel calculations.

The two-channel calculation which predicts an asymmetry parameter governed by the β_{e2} term is found to be in better agreement with the measured values than the one-channel calculation leading to dominant β_{e4} values for bent geometries. Furthermore the larger value of β_{e2} (~ 1) obtained for the more bent geometries is consistent both with the $\beta_e \sim 0.9$ value observed for the MPDI process, and the proposed pathway which invokes dissociation of the more bent component of the NO_2^+ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3$) population. Larger bond angles are associated to lower β_{e2} values which compare well with the $\beta_e \sim 0.3$ measured for non-dissociative MPI. This conclusion is consistent with that of sect. 6, where the measured RFPADs were found better described by the two-channel calculation, although the major FW-BW emission asymmetry which is a fingerprint of these results is not predicted in this calculation.

Finally we note that multiphoton ionization processes displaying similarities with those reported here, including a comparable significant FW-BW asymmetry in the RFPADs, have been attributed to different reactions. Vredenburg *et al* and Form *et al* [24,54] in two-color pump-probe studies with 100 fs pulses at 400 nm and 266 nm assigned a MPDI process corresponding to a similar photoelectron energy $E_e \sim 0.5$ eV and asymmetry parameter $\beta_e \sim 0.9$ to a (3×400 nm + 1×266 nm) ionization process into the NO_2^{+*} (1B_2) dissociative ionic state, for a zero time delay. A related non dissociative MPI process with $\beta_e \sim 0.3$ was attributed to a (1×400 nm + 2×266 nm) reaction pathway, involving PI of a $3p\pi$ state of the $[R^*(6a_1)^{-1}]$ Rydberg series excited by two photon absorption and ionized into the NO_2^{+*} ($X^1\Sigma_g$) ionic state by one 266 nm photon. Using 100 fs pulses at 375 nm, Davies *et al* [23] assigned the zero time delay process in their time-resolved study to a three-photon excitation of the NO_2 molecule to a repulsive potential surface leading to the $\{\text{NO} (C^2\Pi_{1/2}) + \text{O} (^3P_2)\}$ dissociation limit lying at 9.61 eV, and a subsequent ionization of the NO fragment. A similar reaction pathway might also be assumed here, involving a four-photon excitation of such a repulsive state, ultrafast dissociation producing vibrationally excited states of the NO ($C^2\Pi, \nu$) fragment, and one photon ionization of NO ($C^2\Pi_{1/2}, \nu$) into NO^+ ($X^1\Sigma^+, \nu$) at fixed vibrational quantum number. Assuming a prompt dissociation, this process would produce fragments with a maximum recoil energy of about 2.87 eV and an electron energy of $E_e \approx 0.32$ eV, corresponding to the difference between the photon energy and the energy gap between the $\nu = 0$ origins of the NO^+ ($X^1\Sigma^+$) ionic (9.26 eV) and NO ($C^2\Pi$) Rydberg (6.46 eV) states [55]. In such a scheme, the RFPAD would result from MF electron emission from the incipient NO ($C^2\Pi$) molecule [56] remaining space fixed after prompt dissociation from the

four-photon aligned NO₂ molecule, influenced by the presence of the nearby O atom [23]. However, the rather complex vibrational structure of peak A in the MPDI PE energy spectrum indicating the excitation of bending and stretching modes and the comparable MPDI and MPI PE spectra favors the proposed interpretation of ionization into the NO₂⁺ ($X^1\Sigma_g^+, \nu_1, \nu_2, \nu_3$) state, followed by one-photon induced geometry selective dissociation. On the other hand the RFPAD analysis supports the interpretation in terms of photoionization of NO₂ excited states.

9. Conclusion

In this paper we have reported a general analytical expression for the recoil frame photoelectron angular distribution (RFPAD) for multiphoton ionization of a small polyatomic molecule, where the n photon reaction results from $(n-1)$ photon bound-to-bound transitions plus photoionization of a molecular excited state. Taking advantage of the measured ϕ_e azimuthal dependence of the RFPAD, the expression is expanded in recoil frame azimuthal harmonics (RFAH). The $R_K^{(n,RF)}(\chi, \theta_e)$ RFAH bidimensional histograms allow for a sensitive comparison of experimental and theoretical observables and therefore a sensitive probe of the bound-to-bound reaction pathway and the dipole matrix elements characterizing photoionization of the excited state. A more quantitative comparison relying on the $J(\chi)$ and $G(\theta_e)$ one dimensional functions is provided by the principal component analysis (PCA) of the RFAHs.

One-color multiphoton ionization of the NO₂ molecule of C_{2v} (or Cs) symmetry induced by 400 nm femtosecond laser pulses has been selected as a prototype reaction for this study. The motivation is to take advantage of the advanced modelization of the RFPADs as well as of recent calculations including electronic correlations and autoionizing states to elucidate some aspects of the photodynamics of NO₂, such as the role of Rydberg states in electron and nuclear coupled dynamics involving vibronic coupling and/or conical intersections. Analyzing all steps from MFPADs in the molecular frame built on the symmetry axes of the molecule, up to the 5-photon RFPADs, enables us to trace and tentatively interpret the origin of significant emission anisotropies in the recoil frame. The proposed reaction mechanisms provide a coherent picture of the experimental findings. Although all features are not yet well reproduced by the reported calculations, reasonable predictions are achieved: future calculations at different geometries and involving an extended basis set will be performed soon. As for experiments, excitation energies have been extended recently in the 430 nm-375 nm wavelength range [57]: these results will be reported in a forthcoming publication. Finally, it would be of interest to perform time resolved experiments within the 100 fs time window corresponding to the typical duration of the lasers used in this generation of experiments, using e.g., a few fs pump pulse in the UV range exciting one of the [R*(6a₁)⁻¹] or [R*(4b₂)⁻¹] Rydberg series and a probe pulse delayed by few fs, in order to probe the dynamics involving both the linear and bent geometries.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge P. Billaud and Y. J. Picard for their contribution to experiments, S. Damoy, C. Lacan and E. Bouisset from ISMO for their technical support, O. Gobert, J.F. Hergott and the SPAM Laser team members for operating the PLFA laser platform and B. Carré and P. Breger for helpful discussions. We are very grateful to L. Nahon, DESIRS beamline director, and G. Garcia, DESIRS beamline scientist, for a fruitful cooperation, J. F. Gil for technical support and the SOLEIL general staff for operating smoothly the facility.

The support of the PICS (Programme International de Coopération Scientifique CNRS No. 2008-046T) and the Triangle de la Physique (High Rep Image No. 2010-078T, MOF-MPI No. 2013-0569T) is gratefully acknowledged. The SOFOCKLE femtosecond laser is supported by ANR (Agence Nationale de la Recherche, projet Image Femto, N°. ANR-07-BLAN-0162-01). The research leading to these results performed at PLFA laser platform has received funding from LASERLAB-EUROPE (grant agreement n° 284464, EC's Seventh Framework Programme).

We acknowledge the support of the Chemical Sciences, Geosciences and Biosciences Division, Office of Basic Energy Sciences, Office of Science, US Department of Energy and of the R. A. Welch Foundation (Houston, TX) under grant A-1020. Work at LBNL was performed under the auspices of

the US DOE under Contract DE-AC02-05CH11231. This work was also supported by the Texas A&M University Supercomputing Facility.

References

- [1] Reid K L 2012 Photoelectron angular distributions: developments in applications to isolated molecular systems *Mol. Phys.* **110** 131–47
- [2] Dowek D and Lucchese R R 2012 Photoionization Dynamics: Photoemission in the Molecular Frame of Small Molecules Ionized by Linearly and Elliptically Polarized Light *DYNAMICAL PROCESSES IN ATOMIC AND MOLECULAR PHYSICS* vol Chapter 3 (G. Ogurtsov and D. Dowek) pp 57–95
- [3] Hansen J L, Stapelfeldt H, Dimitrovski D, Abu-samha Mahmoud, Martiny C P J and Madsen L B 2011 Time-Resolved Photoelectron Angular Distributions from Strong-Field Ionization of Rotating Naphthalene Molecules *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **106** 073001
- [4] Rouzée A, Kelkensberg F, Siu W K, Gademann G, Lucchese R R and Vrakking M J 2012 Photoelectron kinetic and angular distributions for the ionization of aligned molecules using a HHG source *J. Phys. B At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **45** 074016
- [5] Suzuki Y-I, Tang Y and Suzuki T 2012 Time–energy mapping of photoelectron angular distribution: application to photoionization stereodynamics of nitric oxide *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14** 7309–20
- [6] Hockett P, Staniforth M, Reid K L and Townsend D 2009 Rotationally Resolved Photoelectron Angular Distributions from a Nonlinear Polyatomic Molecule *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **102** 253002
- [7] Saito N, Fanis A D, Kubozuka K, Machida M, Takahashi M, Yoshida H, Suzuki I H, Cassimi A, Czasch A, Schmidt L, Dörner R, Wang K, Zimmermann B, McKoy V, Koyano I and Ueda K 2003 Carbon K-shell photoelectron angular distribution from fixed-in-space CO₂ molecules *J. Phys. B At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **36** L25
- [8] Ullrich J, Moshhammer R, Dorn A, Dörner R, Schmidt L P H and Schmidt-Böcking H 2003 Recoil-ion and electron momentum spectroscopy: reaction-microscopes *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **66** 1463
- [9] Lafosse A, Lebech M, Brenot J C, Guyon P M, Jagutzki O, Spielberger L, Vervloet M, Houver J C and Dowek D 2000 Vector correlations in dissociative photoionization of diatomic molecules in the VUV range: Strong anisotropies in electron emission from spatially oriented NO molecules *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **84** 5987–90
- [10] Bisgaard C Z, Clarkin O J, Wu G, Lee A M, Geßner O, Hayden C C and Stolow A 2009 Time-resolved molecular frame dynamics of fixed-in-space CS₂ molecules *Science* **323** 1464–8
- [11] Hockett P, Bisgaard C Z, Clarkin O J and Stolow A 2011 Time-resolved imaging of purely valence-electron dynamics during a chemical reaction *Nat. Phys.* **7** 612–5
- [12] Fischer A, Sperl A, Cörlin P, Schönwald M, Rietz H, Palacios A, González-Castrillo A, Martín F, Pfeifer T, Ullrich J, Senftleben A and Moshhammer R 2013 Electron Localization Involving Doubly Excited States in Broadband Extreme Ultraviolet Ionization of H₂ *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **110** 213002
- [13] Cryan J P, Glowonia J M, Andreasson J, Belkacem A, Berrah N, Blaga C I, Bostedt C, Bozek J, Buth C, DiMauro L F, Fang L, Gessner O, Guehr M, Hajdu J, Hertlein M P, Hoener M, Kornilov O, Marangos J P, March A M, McFarland B K, Merdji H, Petrović V S, Raman C, Ray D, Reis D, Tarantelli F, Trigo M, White J L, White W, Young L, Bucksbaum P H and Coffee R N 2010 Auger Electron Angular Distribution of Double Core-Hole States in the Molecular Reference Frame *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **105** 083004
- [14] Neidel C, Klei J, Yang C-H, Rouzée A, Vrakking M J J, Klünder K, Miranda M, Arnold C L, Fordell T, L’Huillier A, Gisselbrecht M, Johnsson P, Dinh M P, Suraud E, Reinhard P-G, Despré V, Marques M A L and Lépine F 2013 Probing Time-Dependent Molecular Dipoles on the Attosecond Time Scale *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **111** 033001
- [15] Lucchese R R, Lafosse A, Brenot J C, Guyon P M, Houver J C, Lebech M, Raseev G and Dowek D 2002 Polar and azimuthal dependence of the molecular frame photoelectron angular distributions of spatially oriented linear molecules *Phys. Rev. A* **65** 020702
- [16] Lebech M, Houver J C, Lafosse A, Dowek D, Alcaraz C, Nahon L and Lucchese R R 2003 Complete description of linear molecule photoionization achieved by vector correlations using the light of a single circular polarization *J. Chem. Phys.* **118** 9653–63

- [17] Toffoli D, Lucchese R R, Lebech M, Houver J C and Doweck D 2007 Molecular frame and recoil frame photoelectron angular distributions from dissociative photoionization of NO₂ *J. Chem. Phys.* **126**
- [18] Ruf H, Handschin C, Ferre A, Thire N, Bertrand J B, Bonnet L, Cireasa R, Constant E, Corkum P B, Descamps D, Fabre B, Larregaray P, Mevel E, Petit S, Pons B, Staedter D, Woerner H J, Villeneuve D M, Mairesse Y, Halvick P and Blanchet V 2012 High-harmonic transient grating spectroscopy of NO₂ electronic relaxation *J. Chem. Phys.* **137**
- [19] Arasaki Y, Takatsuka K, Wang K and McKoy V 2010 Time-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy of wavepackets through a conical intersection in NO₂ *J. Chem. Phys.* **132**
- [20] Woerner H J, Bertrand J B, Fabre B, Higuier J, Ruf H, Dubrouil A, Patchkovskii S, Spanner M, Mairesse Y, Blanchet V, Mevel E, Constant E, Corkum P B and Villeneuve D M 2011 Conical Intersection Dynamics in NO₂ Probed by Homodyne High-Harmonic Spectroscopy *Science* **334** 208–12
- [21] Wilkinson I and Whitaker B J 2010 Some remarks on the photodynamics of NO₂ *Annu. Rep. Sect. C Phys. Chem.* **106** 274–304
- [22] Davies J A, LeClaire J E, Continetti R E and Hayden C C 1999 Femtosecond time-resolved photoelectron-photoion coincidence imaging studies of dissociation dynamics *J. Chem. Phys.* **111** 1–4
- [23] Davies J A, Continetti R E, Chandler D W and Hayden C C 2000 Femtosecond time-resolved photoelectron angular distributions probed during photodissociation of NO₂ *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **84** 5983–6
- [24] Vredenburg A, Roeterdink W G and Janssen M H M 2008 Femtosecond time-resolved photoelectron-photoion coincidence imaging of multiphoton multichannel photodynamics in NO₂ *J. Chem. Phys.* **128**
- [25] Elkharrat C, Picard Y J, Billaud P, Cornaggia C, Garzella D, Perdrix M, Houver J C, Lucchese R R and Doweck D 2010 Ion Pair Formation in Multiphoton Excitation of NO₂ Using Linearly and Circularly Polarized Femtosecond Light Pulses: Kinetic Energy Distribution and Fragment Recoil Anisotropy *J. Phys. Chem. A* **114** 13288–13288
- [26] Marggi Poullain S, Veyrinas K, Billaud P, Lebech M, Picard Y J, Lucchese R R and Doweck D 2013 The role of Rydberg states in photoionization of NO₂ and (NO⁺, O⁻) ion pair formation induced by one VUV photon *J. Chem. Phys.* **139** 044311
- [27] Elkharrat C 2010 *Dynamique de photoionisation et de photofragmentation de petites molécules non linéaires* (Institut des Sciences Moléculaires d'Orsay, Université Paris Sud)
- [28] Lebech M, Houver J C and Doweck D 2002 Ion-electron velocity vector correlations in dissociative photoionization of simple molecules using electrostatic lenses *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **73** 1866–74
- [29] Li W B, Montuoro R, Houver J C, Journal L, Haouas A, Simon M, Lucchese R R and Doweck D 2007 Photoemission in the NO molecular frame induced by soft-x-ray elliptically polarized light above the N(1s)(-1) and O(1s)(-1) ionization thresholds *Phys. Rev. A* **75**
- [30] Jagutzki O, Mergel V S, Ullmann-Pfleger K, Spielberger L, Meyer U, Dörner R and Schmidt-Böcking H 1998 Fast Position and Time Resolved Read-Out of Micro-Channelplates with Delay-Line Technique for Single Particle and Photon Detection *Imaging Spectrosc. IV Proc. Int. Symp. Opt. Sci. Eng. Instrum. Proc. SPIE* **3438** 322–34
RoentDek Handels GmbH
- [31] Richard-Viard M, Delboulbé A and Vervloet M 1996 Experimental study of the dissociation of selected internal energy ions produced in low quantities: application to N₂O⁺ ions in the Franck-Condon gap and to small ionic water clusters *Chem. Phys.* **209** 159–67
- [32] Guyétand O, Gisselbrecht M, Huetz A, Agostini P, Carré B, Breger P, Gobert O, Garzella D, Hergott J-F, Tcherbakoff O, Merdji H, Bougeard M, Rottke H, Böttcher M, Ansari Z, Antoine P and DiMauro L F 2008 Complete momentum analysis of multi-photon photo-double ionization of xenon by XUV and infrared photons *J. Phys. B At. Mol. Opt. Phys.* **41** 065601
- [33] Lucchese R R, Raseev G and McKoy V 1982 Studies of differential and total photoionization cross sections of molecular nitrogen *Phys. Rev. A* **25** 2572–87
- [34] Gianturco F, Lucchese R and Sanna N 1994 Calculation of Low-Energy Elastic Cross-Sections for Electron-Cf₄ Scattering *J. Chem. Phys.* **100** 6464–71
- [35] Natalense A P P and Lucchese R R 1999 Cross section and asymmetry parameter calculation for sulfur 1s photoionization of SF₆ *J. Chem. Phys.* **111** 5344–8

- [36] Dunning Jr T H 1989 Gaussian basis sets for use in correlated molecular calculations. I. The atoms boron through neon and hydrogen *J. Chem. Phys.* **90** 1007
- [37] Kendall R A, Dunning Jr T H and Harrison R J 1992 Electron affinities of the first-row atoms revisited. Systematic basis sets and wave functions *J. Chem. Phys.* **96** 6796
- [38] Petsalakis I D, Theodorakopoulos G and Child M S 2001 The Rydberg states of NO₂: Vibrational autoionization of the nd sigma states *J. Chem. Phys.* **115** 10394–403
- [39] Rescigno T N and Orel A E 1991 Continuum basis functions in the complex Kohn variational method *Phys. Rev. A* **43** 1625
- [40] Rescigno T N, Lengsfeld III B H and McCurdy C W 1995 The Incorporation of Modern Electronic Structure Methods in Electron-Molecule Collision Problems: Variational Calculations Using the Complex Kohn Method *Modern Electronic Structure Theory Part I* vol Chapter 9 (World Scientific) pp 501–89
- [41] Werner H-J, Knowles P J, Knizia G, Manby F R, Schütz M, Celani P, Korona and Manby 2003 *Molpro: a package of ab-initio programs* (version 2009.1)
- [42] Lengsfeld III B H and Rescigno T N 1991 Electron-molecule close coupling with correlated target wave functions: Application to impact dissociation of F₂ *Phys. Rev. A* **44** 2913
- [43] Rescigno T N and Orel A E 2013 Theoretical study of excitation of the low-lying electronic states of water by electron impact *Phys. Rev. A* **88** 012703
- [44] Baltzer P, Karlsson L, Wannberg B, Holland D M P, MacDonald M A, Hayes M A and Eland J H D 1998 An experimental study of the valence shell photoelectron spectrum of the NO₂ molecule *Chem. Phys.* **237** 451–70
- [45] Eland J H D and Karlsson L 1998 Dissociative photoionisation of NO₂ up to 26 eV *Chem. Phys.* **237** 139–48
- [46] Irimia D, Petsalakis I D, Theodorakopoulos G and Janssen M H M 2010 Coherent Oscillatory Femtosecond Dynamics in Multichannel Photodynamics of NO₂ Studied by Spatially Masked Electron Imaging *J. Phys. Chem. A* **114** 3157–66
- [47] Schick C P and Weber P M 2001 Ultrafast dynamics in superexcited states of phenol *J. Phys. Chem. A* **105** 3725–34
- [48] Gosselin J L and Weber P M 2005 Rydberg fingerprint spectroscopy: a new spectroscopic tool with local and global structural sensitivity *J. Phys. Chem. A* **109** 4899–904
- [49] Blanchet V, Raffael K, Turri G, Chatel B, Girard B, Garcia I A, Wilkinson I and Whitaker B J 2008 Time-dependent photoionization of azulene: Competition between ionization and relaxation in highly excited states *J. Chem. Phys.* **128** 164318
- [50] Hemberger P, Köhler J, Fischer I, Piani G, Poisson L and Mestdagh J-M 2012 Femtosecond dynamics of cyclopropenylidene, c-C₃H₂ *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **14** 6173–8
- [51] Bigio L, Tapper R and Grant E 1984 The Role of Near-Resonant Intermediate States in the 2-Photon Excitation *J. Phys. Chem.* **88** 1271–3
- [52] Tapper R, Whetten R, Ezra G and Grant E 1984 The Role of Near-Resonant Intermediate States in the 2-Photon Excitation *J. Phys. Chem.* **88** 1273–5
- [53] Knickelbein M, Haber K, Bigio L and Grant E 1986 High-Resolution 2-Photon Spectroscopy of the NO₂ 3p-Sigma-2-Sigma+u(000) Rydberg State *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **131** 51–5
- [54] Form N T, Whitaker B J, Poisson L and Soep B 2006 Time-resolved photoion and photoelectron imaging of NO₂ *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **8** 2925–32
- [55] Huber K P and Herzberg G 1979 *Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure Volumen IV. Constants of diatomic molecules* (Springer US)
- [56] Wang K, Mckoy V and Rudolph H 1994 Rotationally Resolved Photoelectron-Spectra in (2+1) Resonance-Enhanced Multiphoton Ionization of NO Via the C 2Pi Rydberg State *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **217** 490–6
- [57] Marggi Poullain S 2014 *Rôle des états de Rydberg dans la dynamique de photoionisation et de formation de paires d'ions (NO⁺, O⁻) de la molécule NO₂: Photoémission induite par rayonnement synchrotron et impulsions lasers femtosecondes* (Orsay, France: Institut des Sciences Moléculaires d'Orsay, Université Paris Sud)